

UNVEILING THE REASONS BEHIND TEACHERS' EMBRACE OF TRADITIONAL TEACHING METHODS

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Unveiling the Reasons Behind Teachers' Embrace of Traditional Teaching Methods

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Abstract

This qualitative narrative inquiry research aimed on exploring the reasons behind teachers' preference for traditional teaching approaches by conducting interviews with five intermediate teachers from Lagao 2nd Bo. Elementary School as participants. The study revealed that factors contributing to their preference included the convenience of lesson preparation, the low cost of traditional teaching methods, and the familiarity of the classroom environment. The study sought to bridge a gap in the existing literature by offering insights into teachers' perspectives. The findings suggest the need for educational institutions to address these issues and emphasize the importance of teachers gaining first-hand experience in public school classrooms to understand current classroom situation. Furthermore, the research recommends taking steps to promote a deeper understanding of effective instructional practices suitable for present and future educational settings. Overall, the study highlights the factors influencing teachers' preference for traditional approaches to teaching and underscores the importance of addressing these issues to adapt instructional practices to the evolving educational landscape.

Keywords: *traditional approaches to teaching, teacher's preference, teaching methods, narrative inquiry*

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of education, the term "traditional" has often been associated with old beliefs and practices. However, as educators, there is need to recognize the significance of understanding the nuances of this approach in connection to our profession as teachers. This research study aimed to delve deeper understanding on the why's of the teachers' preference for traditional teaching approaches despite exposure to modern pedagogies and strategies.

As a teacher myself, I have witnessed the eagerness of fellow educators to learn and improve through seminars and trainings that introduce them to contemporary teaching styles. Nevertheless, a prevalent dilemma persists among teachers who find it challenging to apply these new methods in real classroom scenarios. The key questions arise: What are the factors that deter some teachers from adopting the latest teaching trends? Is there something intrinsic to being a traditional teacher that fosters this preference?

To address these questions, this research study gathered shared testimonies and perspectives from teachers who lean towards traditional teaching approaches. By understanding their motivations, experiences, and challenges, I aimed to shed light on the reasons behind their inclination toward traditional methods. Furthermore, I explored how factors such as resource limitations, classroom dynamics, and the characteristics of their learners play a role in shaping their teaching practices.

As the educational landscape demands teachers to be adaptive to new trends and cater to diverse learners, it is crucial to identify the underlying reasons for the persistence of traditional teaching approaches. By doing so, we can provide valuable insights to educational administrators, enabling them to devise effective remedies to support teachers in becoming more effective educators. Additionally, this study can serve as a guide for future teachers, preparing them for potential challenges they may encounter in their journey as educators.

In line with the DepEd Order No. 21, Series of 2019 and the Enhanced Basic Education Program, which encourages constructivist, inquiry-based, reflective, collaborative, differentiated, and integrative pedagogical approaches, this research endeavors to contribute to the ongoing pursuit of excellence in education.

However, from the socio-cultural theory by Vygotsky (1978), teachers' preferences are shaped by their cultural backgrounds and experiences. These preferences are influenced by the social and cultural context they grew up in, including their upbringing, education, and societal norms. Teachers often lean towards teaching approaches that align with their beliefs about effective instruction.

Hence, this research study sought to enrich the understanding of teachers' preferences for traditional teaching approaches, foster a dialogue among educators, and ultimately contribute to the improvement of the teaching-learning process for the benefit of both teachers and learners.

Research Objectives

My study aimed to explore the whys of the teachers' preference for traditional approaches to teaching among intermediate teachers at Lagao 2nd Bo. Elementary School. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. Why do teachers prefer to use traditional approaches to teaching?
2. What insights may be drawn from the findings that may explain how traditional approaches facilitate the teaching-learning process?
3. What are factors influencing teachers' preference for traditional teaching approaches?

Literature Review

Traditional Teaching

Gao (2014) asserts that the traditional educational model puts teachers as all knowledgeable beings who teach students to be submissive, lack critical thinking skills, create a hierarchy with the most successful and useful students at the top, and devalue creativity. Furthermore, standardization and stress placed on testing encourages students to memorize information and perform well or else the teacher and school may be punished (Gao, 2014).

Hagenauer et al. (2015) mentioned in their study that the classroom served as a haven for discipline and order. The students, who were seated raptly in rows of oak desks, respected the teacher, a wise and experienced figure. The pupils would pay close attention and take notes as the teacher delivered lectures in front of the classroom. The teacher made extensive use of the students' memorizing abilities and textbooks. The kids would painstakingly research the material given to them, memorizing formulas and data.

From the study of Sieberer-Nagler (2016), the traditional method heavily relied on homework. Assignments were given to the pupils to supplement what they had learned in class. They would spend hours studying textbooks, working through exercises, and producing essays to prove their comprehension. Each submission would be carefully examined by the teacher, who would then offer comments to assist the pupils progress. Exams were common and used to gauge the student's development. The students would study very hard for these tests, going over their notes and textbooks in the hopes of doing well and getting good results. The tests were viewed as a testament to their diligence and hard work. This conventional method of instruction did, however, have certain advantages and disadvantages.

Singhal (2017) stated that education philosophies changed over time, and new teaching strategies that incorporated more participatory and student-centered techniques came into being. Although educators recognize the need to adjust to students' changing requirements in a world that is fast-changing, many still believe that the traditional teaching technique is valuable in some situations.

Delgado et al. (2015) revealed that even though there was an increased effort to put more technology into the classroom, for the better part of the last century, classrooms have generally been based on a traditional, teacher-centered classroom model.

However, other researchers explained that traditional methodology is based largely on a functional procedure that focuses on skills and areas of knowledge in isolation and reduces the integrated process of using a foreign language into sub-sets of discrete skills and areas of knowledge. An interesting point of view expressed by some researchers stated that "In traditional methodology, teaching is deeply teacher-centered."

Shamuratov and Alimbaev (2022), highlight that in traditional methodology "learning was very much seen as under the control of the teacher". Some researchers describe this method as a deductive one: Students are presented with rules and then given opportunities to practice using them." Some traditionalists also argued that with good memory skills, a student can rely on their working memories to grasp the more complicated aspects of problems through a reduction in cognitive load. It was also stated that students can perhaps learn to transfer their prior knowledge more easily and thus gain a "deeper" understanding of the higher content, skills, and strategies.

In the studies of Aljezawi and Albashtawy (2015), they mentioned that in traditional teaching, students receive information through listening and observing while the faculty lectures in front of the classroom. The instructor selects and transmits the knowledge; the student is not actively engaged in the learning process but is a recipient of knowledge.

Based on the research of Bradshaw and Hultquist (2017), with active learning, the teaching is student-centered, and the education focus shifts from the instructor to the student. Accordingly, Chan (2014) argued that this approach gives the student more ownership and control of the learning process, with new information built on past knowledge and experiences. During lectures, teachers are talking while learners are listening. Learning was evaluated by written unit tests or quizzes.

According to Kim et al. (2023), in-class tests or quizzes were the standard methods for evaluating students' performance because they focused more on correct content recall than on the use of reasoning skills. Many classrooms remain teacher-centered, even though there is a concerted effort within segments of society to shift to a more student-centered approach. While each advance in technology has brought new ideas and improvements to the educational setting, the traditional learning environment has remained unchanged from the traditional face-to-face classroom design. Some researchers also argued that traditional teaching models focus on the face-to-face live lectures of teachers and students or small class lectures; if there is an intensive class, the effectiveness of teaching cannot be guaranteed.

Aas (2019) stated that teachers who place a greater emphasis on traditional teaching methods are more likely to pay attention to the unique needs and challenges of their students. The main objective is to transmit academic knowledge using a teacher-centered teaching strategy, which is what puts the emphasis on that. Teachers like this incorporate strategies of targeted intervention and correction into the lessons of their learners. Although challenges are a result of the same teacher organizing lessons in traditional ways, this is supposed to help the learner overcome difficulties.

Meanwhile Aas's (2019) perspective places significant emphasis on the teacher's role in understanding the unique and specific needs of their learners within the context of their learning environment. Such teachers are attuned to the varying abilities, backgrounds, and

learning styles of their students. They use this understanding to tailor their lesson planning and instructional strategies to meet these diverse needs effectively. When these teachers prepare for class, they do not merely add novel strategies or interventions as add-ons or afterthoughts. Instead, they integrate these approaches systematically into their practice. This means that teachers infuse new methodologies, tech applications, or pedagogic strategies throughout their lesson plans, ensuring that these elements are woven into the learning objectives, activities, and assessments.

The underlying idea is that change is not just something to be sprinkled over the top of education but should be deeply embedded within the educational process to be genuinely effective. By fully integrating these changes, the teachers help students connect the dots between different concepts and strategies. This holistic approach can make learning more coherent and relevant, potentially leading to better student engagement and outcomes. It's an approach that speaks to a deep understanding of pedagogy and the dynamism required to remain effective in the ever-changing landscape of education.

In the end, new teaching techniques were constructed using the old teaching strategy as a base. It was crucial in molding generations of students, promoting discipline, and igniting a desire for knowledge. And as the school developed further, it turned into a setting where the best characteristics of tradition and innovation coexisted peacefully, raising well-rounded people prepared to confront the difficulties of a constantly changing world. As mentioned above, we can tell that traditional methodology has negative and positive impacts on the learners, but the decision to use this method of teaching still depends on the teacher.

Modern Teaching

The modern teaching approach has arisen in the constantly changing educational landscape in response to the shifting demands of students in the twenty-first century. In order to offer compelling and individualized educational experiences, this strategy embraces cutting-edge technologies, collaborative learning, and student-centered pedagogy (Bernard et al., 2019).

The incorporation of technology into instruction is one of its most important components. Teachers use a variety of digital materials and tools to improve their lessons and make learning more engaging and accessible. Technology has transformed the classroom, allowing students to explore, create, and engage with material in previously inconceivable ways. Examples include interactive whiteboards, instructional apps, online learning platforms, and virtual reality simulations (Ren et al., 2015).

Student-centered learning is emphasized in modern instruction as well. Students are urged to participate actively in their education rather than just receiving information passively. Teachers serve as facilitators, leading students through projects based on inquiry, activities for problem-solving, and group discussions. With this method, children learn to explore their own interests, think independently, and collaborate with others in productive ways. It also encourages critical thinking, creativity, and communication skills Estai and Bunt (2016).

Enhancing students' autonomy during the learning process encourages their active participation in experiential learning, which is characterized by a continuous cycle of experimentation, error, and subsequent rectification. According to Rahmawati et al. (2019), this particular approach promotes the development of creative thinking skills and enhances the achievement of significant learning outcomes.

The acceptance of individual variations and various learning styles is another aspect of contemporary education. Every kid has different needs and strengths, so teachers work hard to establish inclusive classrooms that cater to those. Diverse teaching resources, flexible grouping, personalized learning plans, and other differentiation tactics make sure that every student has the chance to achieve and realize their full potential.

Additionally, contemporary instruction encourages the acquisition of 21st century skills and lifelong learning. Beyond acquiring subject-specific knowledge, it emphasizes developing soft skills like cooperation, critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy. These abilities are crucial for success in a world that is becoming more linked and complex, where the capacity to evaluate information, think critically, and adapt to new circumstances is crucial.

Education is the foundation of our civilization's success. Ever since, it has been accepted that teaching is indeed a noble profession. The teachers are expected to do their best to impart, convey, and receive information correctly from their learners in class. Along with improvements made to the educational system for learners, the general environment of classroom instruction is changing in the 21st century as well. Modern educators are aware that every student is unique and has a distinct level of knowledge and comprehension. The learner is at the center of modern instructional methods. Saada and Gross (2019) also stated that the utilization of modern teaching methods in the field of education contributed to the advancement of teaching and learning.

A modern method of teaching is also known as a constructivist approach since it involves learners actively taking part in the entire process as they increase their knowledge and develop their abilities. It is now necessary for students to adopt modern teaching techniques, which will also serve to lessen student competitiveness, foster teamwork, and improve the quality of the learning environment. Strategies required for ongoing improvement in the current educational system require information and adaptation. Boncea (2016) mentioned that the most effective methods for achieving this goal are contemporary teaching methods, which allow kids to access knowledge and grow in terms of their intellectual prowess, skills, aptitudes, talents, feelings, and emotions.

In accordance with Al-Sabhi (2018), modern approaches to instruction change depending on various pedagogical personality traits. While Kostadinovska-Stojchevska and Popovikj (2019), stated that educators who base their work on a student-centered strategy and work to ensure that everyone, including the highly brilliant and those with special needs, receives a high-quality education through the effectiveness of proposed approaches, educational differentiation, cultural relevance, social-emotional learning, and pertinent information.

In their 2019 study, Huang et al. acknowledged the significance of appropriate implementation and pedagogical alignment while reporting positive results in terms of student motivation, information access, and interactive learning experiences. However, for Bietenbeck (2014), a contemporary teaching strategy has a positive and significant effect on students' reasoning capacity while having no effect on their knowledge or problem-solving skills.

In general, modern teaching methodology integrates technology, learner-centered instruction, personalization, 21st century skills, and holistic development. It attempts to prepare students for a future where flexibility, critical thinking, teamwork, and lifelong learning will be necessary by adjusting to the demands of the digital world. Modern teaching aims to create dynamic and engaging learning environments through the use of new methods, giving students the tools, they need to become active learners and responsible members of society.

To sum up the above-mentioned ideas about modern methodology, we can highlight student-centered interaction, which is connected to the learner's involvement in everything going on during the delivery of the lesson. This shifts the teacher's role to not causing the learning but helping it happen. The teacher's task is to choose activities suitable for their learners, to guide them in the lessons, and to encourage them to experiment with the language. The modern methodology of teaching comprises a rich variety of pedagogies that should have some common features: activities involving students and closeness to real-life situations.

The Whys of the Teachers' Preferences for Traditional Approaches to Teaching

Chen and Xiao (2021) mentioned in their study that teachers' preferences for traditional approaches to teaching might have a variety of origins, including personal experiences, educational ideals, and perceptions of their efficacy. Since many teachers received their education through the old ways, they may feel more at ease and competent utilizing these strategies today. The planning of classes, classroom management, and content delivery can all be facilitated for teachers by familiarity with classical teaching techniques.

Traditional teaching strategies frequently offer a structured framework for instruction, with responsibilities and expectations for both teachers and students made explicit. Some teachers favor this structure because it encourages orderly learning environments, allows for efficient time management, and helps maintain classroom discipline (Lazarides et al., 2020).

In the opinion of Wei et al. (2020), in traditional teaching methods, the teacher serves as the student's main source of information and instruction. Because they feel it gives them greater control over the learning process, maintains their position of authority in the classroom, and ensures that a specific topic is addressed completely, some teachers may favor this strategy. Discipline, respect for authority, and attention to norms are frequently emphasized in traditional teaching methods. These components, in the opinion of some teachers, are necessary for fostering responsibility in pupils and fostering a focused learning environment.

From the statement of Murillo-Zamorano et al. (2019) conventional teaching strategies are frequently linked to a concentration on academic material and the mastery of particular abilities and competencies. Some professors might think that using these strategies gives students a more demanding academic experience and better prepares them for exams or future academic endeavors. In some educational environments, teachers may not have as much access to technology, materials, or training as they would like to use more cutting-edge or creative teaching strategies. As a result, they might favor teacher-centered instruction or more conventional approaches that use fewer resources.

Through efficient professional development programs, Sarsenbaevich (2023) emphasized the need to assist teachers in adjusting to current teaching methodologies while highlighting the necessity for continued training, resources, and pedagogical assistance. In addition to that, Lee et al. (2019), in their discussion of the digital divide and the effects of uneven access to technology, emphasized the necessity for equitable access to support the effectiveness of contemporary teaching strategies across a range of student populations. The world of education is beginning to recognize that, despite some teachers' preferences for traditional methods of instruction, a more student-centered and creative approach can better fulfill the variety of requirements of 21st century learners. More contemporary and adaptable teaching methods are being investigated and promoted through educational research and changing pedagogical practices.

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, it is essential for educators to engage in a thorough evaluation of the myriad teaching methodologies available to them. This reflective process involves weighing the potential advantages and shortcomings of each instructional approach in light of the desired educational outcomes they intend to achieve. Educators must thoughtfully consider which methods align most effectively with their specific learning goals, considering the unique needs and anticipated performance levels of their students.

Additionally, educators must also make pragmatic assessments about the practicality of these methods, given the resources they have at their disposal. This careful deliberation ensures that educators can make informed decisions that not only cater to the scholastic objectives they aim to fulfill but also optimize the educational experience for their students, tailoring their pedagogical strategies to

foster an environment that is conducive to learning.

In our generation today, we educators are encountering many challenges in deciding which methods suit best in organizing and delivering instruction to learners with different needs and multiple intelligences. The pedagogies and methods used play an important role in developing more effective instruction in diverse classrooms. Hence, we teachers have the freedom to choose any ways, techniques, and strategies of teaching that we are comfortable with and teaching styles that suit and are more effective for our learners.

Methodology

Research Design

My study explored the whys of the teachers' preferences for the traditional approaches to teaching at the intermediate level of Lagao 2nd Bo. Elementary. Further, this study employs the descriptive approach of a qualitative research design. From the study of Creswell (2014), qualitative research is characterized as a methodical process of gathering, analyzing, and interpreting data with the aim of generating descriptive accounts and explanations of social phenomena and research objectives within their authentic contexts. This particular form of research entails the depiction and analysis of the cultural and behavioral aspects exhibited by the participants under study.

The goal is to collect information that is rich in both context and detail. When there is a need to investigate complicated occurrences or learn more about the experiences and viewpoints of individuals about a certain subject, qualitative research is frequently utilized. It is particularly helpful when researchers seek to understand the meaning that individuals attach to their experiences or attempt to identify the underlying causes of people's conduct.

Charmaz and Thornberg (2020) defined qualitative research as a method that aims to understand and interpret social phenomena by studying individual and group experiences and meanings from their point of view. Qualitative research places a strong emphasis on the significance of researching the experiences that individuals have really gone through in addition to the social processes that create those experiences.

A research strategy known as narrative inquiry is a qualitative research methodology that focuses on the study of the stories or narratives that people tell about their experiences. As a researcher using narrative inquiry, I would collect personal stories from individuals through interviews, written accounts, or other means, and then analyze these narratives to identify common themes, meanings, and interpretations. This approach allows me to explore the unique perspectives and lived experiences of the participants, providing valuable insight into the research topic. Additionally, narrative inquiry often involves a reflexive and iterative process, allowing for a deep and nuanced understanding of the human experience as it relates to the research question.

Participants

My study involved five (5) intermediate teachers who were teaching Grade 4, Grade 5, and Grade 6 students at Lagao 2nd Bo. Elementary School in the school year 2022-2023. The teachers were purposefully selected.

For the purpose of confidentiality, I used corresponding codes to represent my participants. I used the following codes for my teacher participants: T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5. All of them are residents of Barangay San Isidro, General Santos City, and teachers of Lagao 2nd Bo. Elementary School.

Instruments

In selecting the participants, purposive sampling was used for it provided a focused and intentional approach to selecting the intermediate teachers. I decide to use purposive sampling to select educators who are known for integrating innovative tech into their lessons. I'm looking for those who are at the forefront of this trend since they can provide deeper insights into my topic. Purposive sampling allowed me to choose participants who prefers traditional approaches to teaching which is relevant to the research topic. In this case, I was interested in understanding the underlying reasons behind teachers' preference for traditional teaching approaches. By selecting intermediate teachers who were well-acquainted with both traditional and modern teaching methods, I gained insights into their perspectives, experiences, and beliefs regarding traditional approaches.

Additionally, purposive sampling ensured that the participants had the necessary knowledge and expertise to provide meaningful and relevant information for the study. Intermediate teachers were more likely to have a deeper understanding of pedagogical methods and the reasons behind their instructional choices. I acquired rich and in-depth data from participants who were most appropriate for answering the research questions making use of purposive sampling. This sampling method makes it possible to conduct a thorough investigation into the motivating factors behind teachers' preference for traditional approaches, building up the likelihood of gaining significant insights that could impact educational practices and policy.

Procedure

Before I began collecting data, I wrote a letter to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent, requesting permission to conduct the study with my target school and participants. This communication was issued before the data gathering procedure began. Upon

approval, I personally sought permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS), to which our school belongs. After receiving approval from the PSDS, I requested permission to carry out the research from the principal of the school and then went on to meet with the class advisers.

Then, I provided my participants with an overview of how the research was conducted and asked them about their preferences on the schedule of their individual interviews. After completing the tasks outlined in the plan, I went back to the school and began conducting interviews with the participants. Through in-depth interviews, rich descriptions from the perspective of participants are obtained. From the analysis of their stories, a number of themes are discernible.

I collected and investigated the experiences of elementary intermediate teachers by using an interview guide in order to capture information that may not be observed directly. This provided information regarding the participants' insights and experiences of the world in which they worked, as well as the significance that the participants attributed to these experiences.

While conducting the interviews, I created an atmosphere that encouraged my participants to voice their opinions and narrate their experiences in a manner they found most coherent. Structured around questions pertinent to my research, this approach simultaneously offered my participants the latitude to reflect upon and share stories pertinent to the topic. This method facilitated the elicitation of rich, detailed accounts, allowing for an in-depth exploration of their experiences. The conversations were carefully yet flexibly guided to ensure relevance to the research objectives while honoring the unique perspectives each informant brought to the study.

During the interviews, it gives the teachers the chance to convey their personal stories and express their ideas in a way that is valuable for them, and it gives them the ability to express themselves freely. It is constructed with particular questions that are pertinent to this study, and it also gives the participants the opportunity to reflect on their own experiences that are related to the topic at hand.

After the interview was over, I went back and transcribed each response I had gotten from my participants. In addition to that, I provided them with a copy of the transcripts so that they may investigate, validate, and verify the information that was recorded. Every single one of the participants' extended their blessing. My participants were required to sign a verification form in order to provide documentation of their participation. In the end, I did a thematic analysis of the transcripts from the interviews I had with the individuals that I had previously completed.

Ethical Considerations

I ensured that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by the Holy Trinity College because it helped to avoid engaging in practices which may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those whom I sought to do research with.

Adhering to these guidelines was of paramount importance as it safeguarded against any potential harm or exploitation of the individuals involved in my research. By strictly abiding by the ethical considerations, I ensured that my study was conducted with integrity, respect, and the utmost regard for the rights and well-being of the participants. The ethical guidelines provided a framework that guided my research process, ensuring that I upheld the principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, and justice.

Moreover, I took careful measures to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participants. Informed consent was obtained from all individuals involved, ensuring they were fully aware of the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of their participation. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. I anonymized any identifiable information to maintain confidentiality and anonymity throughout the research process.

By adhering to these ethical considerations, I not only fulfilled my responsibilities as a researcher but also upheld the dignity and rights of the individuals I worked with.

Informed Consent. As a researcher, obtaining informed consent from participants is a fundamental ethical requirement in my study. Before the commencement of my study, I provide prospective participants with detailed information regarding the study's purpose, procedures, and potential benefits. They are thoroughly informed about their rights throughout the research process, including the option to withdraw their participation at any point. I also present them with a comprehensive overview of the data collection procedures.

Prior to conducting the study, I ensure that participants sign the consent form, acknowledging their understanding and agreement to participate. The consent forms specify the goal, length, methods, potential hazards, advantages, confidentiality measures, and contact information in case of questions or concerns. I make certain that the permission forms follow ethical principles and legislation and are easy for participants to read.

Voluntary Participation. I placed a high value on and prioritized voluntary engagement in my study. I guaranteed that this concept was followed by placing a high value on gaining participants' informed permission. I emphasized to participants that their participation was fully voluntary and that they had the freedom to decline or withdraw at any time without penalty. I placed a high value on the privacy and confidentiality of the personal data provided by participants.

I offered detailed information on the study, including its aims, procedures, and expected outcomes. I appreciated and respected participants' autonomy. This included recognizing their ability to make their own judgments and supporting their right to self-determination. I recognized that consent was a dynamic process, and I always sought confirmation from participants that they were

willing to continue participating in the study.

Data Privacy. Data privacy is of the utmost importance in my research. I prioritize the protection and confidentiality of participants' personal information throughout the entire research process.

I ensured data privacy by obtaining informed consent from participants and clearly explaining how their personal data will be collected, used, and protected. I outlined the specific measures taken to ensure confidentiality and reassure participants that their information will only be used for research purposes.

To safeguard privacy, I employed techniques such as anonymization and pseudonymization. Personal identifiable information is removed or replaced with unique identifiers, ensuring that individuals cannot be identified directly from the data. This protects the privacy of participants and reduces the risk of re-identification. I stored the research data securely, using encryption and access controls to protect against unauthorized access. Data is stored on password-protected and encrypted devices or on secure servers with restricted access. Physical documents are kept in locked cabinets or secure storage facilities.

When sharing or disseminating research findings, I take precautions to preserve privacy. I present aggregated or de-identified data, removing any information that may potentially identify participants. This prevents any unintended disclosure of sensitive information. I seek ethical review and approval from the appropriate review board or ethics committee. This review process helps ensure that my data privacy measures are aligned with ethical guidelines and protect the rights and privacy of participants.

Finally, I established clear protocols for data retention and destruction. I retain data only for the necessary duration required by regulations or institutional policies. After the retention period, I securely and permanently delete or dispose the data to prevent unauthorized access. By implementing these data privacy measures, I prioritized the confidentiality and security of participants' personal information. Respecting data privacy not only protected the rights and well-being of individuals but also promoted trust and enabled participants to feel confident in sharing their data for research purposes.

Gender Sensitivity. I recognized the importance of gender sensitivity in my research, which involved considering the influence of gender on various aspects of the study. By incorporating gender sensitivity into my research, I aimed to contribute to a more inclusive and equitable understanding of the topic. This involved recognizing and addressing gender-related biases, stereotypes, and power dynamics while valuing the diverse experiences and perspectives of individuals of all genders.

I ensured that my research includes a diverse representation of genders. This involved actively seeking participation from individuals of different genders, including women, men, and non-binary individuals. By doing so, I aimed to capture a comprehensive understanding of experiences and perspectives related to the research topic. I recognized that gender intersects with other social identities such as race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and sexuality. I took an intersectional approach to understanding the complex ways in which these identities intersect and influence the research topic. This helped to capture a more nuanced understanding of experiences and avoid generalizations or stereotypes.

To add to that, I am attentive to power dynamics related to gender, particularly in situations where gender disparities or hierarchies exist. I strived to create an inclusive and respectful research environment that allows for equitable participation and reduces power differentials between the researcher and participants. I analyzed and interpreted the data in a way that acknowledges and accounts for gender-related factors. This included examining potential gender differences, similarities, and patterns in the data and reporting findings in a manner that accurately reflects the diversity of gender experiences.

Lastly, I actively collaborated and consulted experts or stakeholders who have expertise in gender-related issues. This helped to ensure that my research is sensitive to gender dynamics and aligned with current knowledge and best practices in the field.

Cultural Sensitivity. Cultural sensitivity is a fundamental principle that guides my approach throughout the entire research process. It encompasses a set of values and practices aimed at recognizing, respecting, and valuing the cultural diversity and perspectives of the individuals and communities I study. Cultural sensitivity is not just a checkbox to mark off; it is an ongoing commitment to foster inclusivity and ensure that my research is conducted in an ethical and respectful manner.

To guarantee cultural sensitivity, I aggressively sought feedback and collaboration from community members and cultural specialists who might contribute significant insights and viewpoints. Their advice assisted me in navigating any traps, biases, or misinterpretations that may have developed throughout the study process. By incorporating them in the study design and implementation, I hoped to co-create knowledge and guarantee that the research was respectful, relevant, and matched with the needs and ambitions of the community.

In conclusion, cultural sensitivity was not an afterthought in my research; it was a key value that pervaded all aspects of my work. I hoped to have conducted research that respected and represented the different cultural viewpoints of the participants, promoted inclusion, and contributed to the overall well-being and empowerment of the communities I investigated by embracing cultural sensitivity.

Health and Safety Protocols. I prioritized the health and safety of both myself and the participants involved in my research. Implementing robust health and safety protocols is crucial to ensuring a secure and ethical research environment. Before initiating my research, I conducted a comprehensive risk assessment to identify potential hazards and evaluate their likelihood and severity. This

assessment helped me develop strategies to mitigate risks and safeguard the well-being of all individuals involved. I strictly adhered to ethical guidelines set forth by relevant institutions and regulatory bodies. These guidelines ensured that my research respected the rights, dignity, and privacy of participants while minimizing any potential physical or psychological harm.

Prior to involving participants in my research, I obtained their informed consent. This included providing clear and concise information about the nature of the study, its objectives, potential risks, and benefits. Participants had the right to ask questions, fully understand the research process, and make an informed decision about their participation. By integrating these health and safety protocols into my research, This approach not only safeguarded individuals but also contributed to the credibility and validity of my research findings.

Results and Discussion

Reasons for Teachers' Preference in Using the Traditional Approaches to Teaching

Table 1 presents the major themes, core ideas, and frequency of responses by teachers with regard to the reasons behind their preference for traditional teaching approaches.

Table 1. Reasons for Teachers' Preference in Using the Traditional Approaches to Teaching

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Frequency of Responses</i>
Convenience in Lesson Preparation	Instructional Materials are Easy to Prepare	General
Inexpensiveness of Traditional Teaching	Instructional Materials are Cheaper	General
Old School Classroom Setting	Lack of Technological Teaching Aids	General

Upon examining the information of the data gathered on teachers' preference for making use of traditional teaching approaches, as seen in Table 1, three major themes have emerged. These are the Convenience in Lesson Preparation, the Inexpensiveness of Traditional Teaching, and the Old School Classroom Setting. The aforementioned emerging themes were derived from the responses provided by the participants, elucidating their preference for utilizing traditional teaching approaches.

One of the themes that showed up in the discussion of why teachers prefer to use traditional approaches to teaching is the Inexpensiveness of Traditional Teaching. As a result, the core idea my participants expressed is that instructional materials are cheaper, which elicited a general response from the participants. One more theme that was brought up was the Old School Classroom Setting, which came up with the core idea of the lack of technological teaching aids. This core idea also got general responses from the participants.

Convenience in Lesson Preparation

The first major theme that was brought out in the reasons why teachers prefer traditional approaches to teaching was convenience in lesson preparation. This major theme gathered general responses from the participants. Using a traditional teaching approach is convenient for them when preparing their lessons. Some of them even mentioned that with the use of a traditional approach to teaching, it is easier and more hassle-free when it comes to the preparation of their lessons.

Instructional Materials are Easy to Prepare. The core idea that emerged on the major theme of convenience in lesson preparation is that instructional materials are easy to prepare, which gathered a general response from the participants.

The lines below are the reasons why T4 prefers traditional approaches to teaching.

Ahh for me, my reasons for preferring the use of traditional approaches in teaching ahh materials are easy to prepare and ahh pupils are my students can easily get what I am teaching or what I am going to persuade about the lessons that I have because they can visualize easily what are or what is the lesson all about. (T4, Lines 20-23)

T4 shared her experience and mentioned that the reason she prefers the traditional teaching approach is because the materials are easy to prepare for her as a teacher, and for her, the students can easily get, persuade, and visualize what the lesson is about.

According to Ng'entu (2019), lesson preparation determines the outcome of every lesson. Instructional materials play a big part in supporting learners' educational development. Odinakachi et al. (2023), as a result of their study, stated that adequate instructional resources should be provided for effective teaching and studying processes.

In an interview, T1 stated her reasons for preferring traditional approaches.

Hmm I think the advantage of traditional teaching is that, as a teacher, its hassle free. Of course, ahh it does not require a lot of money and its much easier to provide the instructional materials. Traditional teaching is more advantageous for real scenario in public school because in reality, we are not yet ready because we lack all resources and a fund. (T1, Lines 50-53)

T1 shared that the traditional teaching approach for her as a teacher is hassle-free in terms of preparing her lesson.

To add to that, T2 also shared her experience with choosing traditional approaches to teaching. The statement of T2 is shown below.

Well, considering the time of preparations for the lessons, I think it's more convenient if I use traditional method. Not only I'm using

chalk and talk but I also use I also use some materials which are not related to technology like using cartolinas, or bond papers and other an activities prepared in paper rather than using technologies. Since in other classroom, in the classroom that I'm teaching are not connected with Wi-Fi, it's difficult to adopt to modern techniques of teaching and I think, even though I'm using the traditional method of teaching they the students also enjoy doing those things in groupings because they can manipulate the things in a traditional way like using pens, and-- papers, and-- glue and scissors. I think that would be fun for some learners because some of them are not customized with technology also. (T2, Lines 32-41)

Based on the experiences of T2, she mentioned that a traditional teaching approach is more convenient on her part as a teacher considering the time spent preparing for the lesson because she is using materials that are not related to technology, such as cartolinas and bond papers, in her teaching. She also mentioned that it is difficult to adopt modern teaching techniques because there is no internet connection in the classroom. For her, even though she is using the traditional approaches to teaching, the students are still enjoying those grouping activities because they can manipulate the materials like pens, papers, glue, and scissors. She has mentioned that it is somewhat fun for the students.

Inexpensiveness of Traditional Teaching

The second major theme that I have gathered based on the participants responses on why they prefer a traditional approach to teaching is the inexpensiveness of traditional teaching.

The inexpensiveness of traditional teaching refers to the low cost associated with traditional instructional methods. It means that traditional teaching approaches typically do not require significant financial investments or the use of expensive resources. Instead, they rely on more traditional and commonly available teaching materials and strategies, such as textbooks, chalkboards, and face-to-face interactions. The inexpensiveness of traditional teaching makes it a cost-effective option, particularly in settings with limited resources or budget constraints.

Instructional Materials are Cheaper. The core idea that was brought up from the major theme, Inexpensiveness of Traditional Teaching, is that instructional materials are cheaper.

The experience shared by T1 revealed that she does not have enough budget to suffice the expenses needed for the production of instructional materials in the 21st century teaching. The lines below are T1's statement.

Ahmm, Of course, it's the modern way of teaching. As I've said, it is more relevant to the learners. Hmm but, I'm sorry to say this, I don't have a choice to use the traditional teaching approach. This is ahh the only or this is the easier approach that doesn't need much resources because, to be honest, I don't have enough budget to suffice the expenses needed for the production of instructional materials in the 21st century teaching. It's okay to spend for a day, but it will be a burden if I will do it daily. I have my family, so, I have to prioritize my family. (T1, Lines 42-47)

T1 answered the question of which is better, the traditional approach or the modern way of teaching. She shared that, as shown in her statement above, the modern way of teaching is better, but she does not have a choice but to choose the traditional teaching approach because, as for her, this is the easier approach that does not need much resources. She shared that she does not have enough budget to cover the expenses needed for the production of instructional materials in 21st century teaching.

T4 shared her statement in relation to her preference of the traditional approaches to teaching in the lines below.

So, we cannot materialize or we cannot use that kind of application, even though we are very eager to use that since we are now in the 21st century, but then, as a teacher, ahh I still use the traditional approaches. Ahh why? Because, ah like what I've said, wala tayong (we don't have) materials but then ang pupils is mas madali silang maka learn (the pupils can easily learn). Noh! we can pinpoint easily what are we going to taught or what are we going to teach to them and then, we can provide them easily the materials like those ahh paper, flashcards, charts and everything. So, that's it. (T4, Lines 41-51)

T4 shared that, with a traditional approach to teaching, she can easily provide her learners with the materials she needs to deliver her lessons. These materials are paper, flashcards, charts, etc.

From to the study of Adeyanju (2014), learning can take place as a result of newly acquired skills, principles, perceptions, knowledge, facts, and information that are currently available. An individual's capacity to learn can be improved by utilizing a variety of teaching and learning materials due to the fact that these resources excite, motivate, and concentrate the attention of learners for a period of time during the instructional process.

T2 seems to support T1's statement. The statement below is T2's shared experiences.

Hmm for now, I would say ahmm both are the best but in my in my case, I would choose traditional way of teaching because ahmm you have to consider your the finances, of course. Ahmm the materials that you have ahmm and and the level of students that we have ahmm because if you will going to use the other the modern type of the modern strategies you have to invest on on buying computers computer or loading your your wifi and they can learn if they have also their devices for for for learning. But in the traditional way, they can use paper and pen or manila paper and and pentel pens or paste or glue in doing their activities, its manipulative at the same

time they were learning a lot. It's not it doesn't mean that traditional that it's the teacher who always does the job but ahh using the traditional way of teaching by using ahmm paper and pens and other other things that are not related to technology, I think it also delivers learning to ahh learners in a different way. (T2, Lines 61-71)

T2 mentioned that both traditional and modern ways of teaching are the best, but in her case, she chooses the traditional way of teaching because she also considers her finances and the materials that she has. She stated in her response that if she will use modern strategies, she has to invest in buying a computer and load your Wi-Fi.

According to her, the learners also have their own devices for learning. In a traditional way, the learners can use paper, pens, manila papers, pentel pens, glue, or paste in doing their activities, which for her is manipulative, and at the same time, the students were learning a lot. She also added that the traditional way of teaching also delivers learning to the learners in a different way.

T5 also mentioned in his response on the lines below.

Ahh basically, ahmm when the time na nag tudlo ko sa (I started to teach in) elementary it has it has been my ahh practical way of teaching student ahmm first of all yung yung libro kasi (it is the book) books is my primary sources. So, therefore, lahat nang lessons na ginagamit ko (all the lesson that I am using) are all inside the book. Kahit na dumating pa yung K-12 (even though the K-12 was pushed through) ahh I still prefer to use ahh the books ahh other books aside from the government issued issued books because from from this books ahmm ahh for me it so praktikal kasi (because it is practical) ahh when we use ahh different different kinds of sources. (T5, Lines 16-23)

T5 shared that he prefers a practical way of teaching and uses books as his primary sources. He mentioned that he prefers a traditional teaching approach because, for him, he is just being realistic about what is available inside the classroom.

Old School Classroom Setting

The Old School Classroom Setting was the last major theme that was brought up from the participants' responses on why they prefer a traditional approach to teaching, with the core idea being the Inexpensiveness of traditional teaching. Since the beginning of the development of information technology, traditional classrooms have been in competition with the increasingly common virtual classroom. For students who wish to earn a degree more quickly and inexpensively, online courses are an alternative to traditional classroom settings. Nevertheless, a lot of students believe that social skill development and learning take place more effectively in typical classroom settings.

Lack of Technological Teaching Aids. Sun and Chen (2016) mentioned in their study that online education is expected to become the standard method of providing education in the digital age. In a traditional classroom setting, some students are unable to participate in online classes due to a lack of access to technological devices or familiarity with their usage. In this environment, learning primarily relies on the teacher imparting knowledge to the students through discussions and interactions. The process often concludes with students recording the new information in their notebooks. For students pursuing specializations unrelated to technology, printed courses and books from the library are generally sufficient for their learning needs.

Based on the response of T1, teachers are not provided with the 21st classroom facilities that they need, the statements below are her experience. The contributing influence that made me engross with the use of traditional teaching is the real scenario, the real classroom situation. The real scenario is there is no computers, no projector, no internet connection, no printer, no papers. Oh my god. They only provide trainings to teachers, but no materials provided. Maybe there are some, but not enough. Sometimes this comes to my mind, "is my salary intended for the instructional materials?". That is the real scenario. I just adopt on it. (T1, Lines 61-66)

As the experiences shared by T1, she mentioned that they are not provided with the educational classroom facilities such computers, internet connections, printers and papers that made her engrossed with the traditional approach to teaching. She even mentioned that they are only provided with training but the materials they need inside the classroom are not provided.

In addition, the response of T4 tells that the instructional materials are not provided that is why she for her students she still prefers the traditional teaching approach.

In the other way, it has a lot of differences because today we are in the ahh we are now in the 21st century, of course, we need to be equipped with the high tech high technologies like ahh using laptop, others other teachers ahh our school using tablet in learning or what we say there are a lots of ahh apps in the com ahh the in the internet we can use as a teachers for providing our students to learn or to be or to capture their interest in learning but then, since we don't have enough of this, ahh like for example, the internet connectivity, so, the school or even our principal cannot provide ahh internet connection in every classroom. So, we cannot materialize or we cannot use that kind of application, even though we are very eager to use that since we are now in the 21st century, but then, as a teacher, ahh I still use the traditional approaches. Ahh why? Because, ah like what I've said, wala tayong (we don't have) materials but then ang pupils is mas madali silang maka maka learn (the pupils can easily learn). Noh! we can pinpoint easily what are we going to taught or what are we going to teach to them and then, we can provide them easily the materials like those ahh paper, flashcards, charts and everything. So, that's it. (T4, Lines 38-51)

From the statements of T4, she mentioned that since they are in 21st century, as teachers, they need to be equipped with the high

technologies such as using laptop and with internet connection but in her school these materials are not provided. In these situations, careful planning and execution are required. Other stakeholders, such as students and administration, should be concerned about overcoming perceived limits in online education. The statement below is the shared experiences of T2 on why she preferred traditional approaches to teaching.

Well, first is the time because of the busy schedule, you have to consider your family, your time, your ancillary, and also, one reason is would be the resources, of course, because ahmm its it's the fund that is lacking and the equipment and the resources are lacking. (T2, Lines 85-87)

From the statement of T2, she considered her schedule, family, time, ancillary and the resources in preferring the traditional approaches to teaching. She said that the fund, the equipment's and the resources are lacking. Thus, upon scrutinizing her, she is much willing to utilize 21st century teaching approach if the instructional materials are provided.

Insights Drawn from the Findings that may Explain How the Traditional Approaches Facilitate the Teaching-Learning Process

Table 2 presents the major themes that emerged, the core ideas and the frequency of responses which I based from my participants' responses. The first theme that come out from my participants is Traditional Teaching Promotes Holistic Teaching-Learning Process with core ideas Facilitates Direct Instruction which gathered variant responses, Inculcates Discipline with typical responses and Enhances Learner Engagements which gathered general responses. The second major theme that emerge was Traditional Teaching is a Practical Way of Teaching which come up with three core ideas. First, it Employs Realistic Way of Teaching that gathered typical responses. Next, it Encourages Memorization which gathered variant responses. Lastly, it Stimulates Resourcefulness of Teachers which gathered typical responses from the participants.

Table 2. *Insights Drawn from the Findings that may Explain How the Traditional Approaches Facilitate the Teaching-Learning Process*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Frequency of Responses</i>
Traditional Teaching Promotes Holistic Teaching-Learning Process	Facilitates Direct Instruction	Variant
	Inculcates Discipline	Typical
	Enhances Learner Engagements	General
Traditional Teaching is a Practical Way of Teaching	Employs Realistic way of Teaching	Typical
	Encourages Memorization	Variant
	Stimulates Resourcefulness of Teachers	Typical

Traditional Teaching Promotes Holistic Teaching-Learning Process

The traditional teaching approach promotes holistic learning through several key elements. It adheres to an organized curriculum that includes a wide range of courses, ensuring that students acquire a well-rounded education. It provides a solid foundation for critical thinking and higher-level learning by emphasizing the principles and essentials of each subject. Teachers have a critical role in supporting thorough learning of complicated issues as the major source of knowledge and advice.

Facilitates Direct Instruction. The first core idea that came up from the major theme, Traditional Teaching Promotes Holistic Teaching which gathered variant responses from the participants. In my study, Learning Process of direct instruction is a teaching method in which the teacher is in control for the learning of all students and plays an active part.

T3 shared her experiences on how traditional approaches to teaching facilitates the teaching-learning process as stated in the lines below.

Ahh in I think its ano (what) its traditional teaching because it's a one-way flow of information or direct instruction to the learners. In the traditional teaching approach, we can train the way we wanted to and, in that way, we can impose discipline effectively, we can focus on the content of the lesson and also, we can see the learners will strive hard to meet their standard and get high scores ahh and please the teacher and also, they can pass the requirements. (T3, Lines 39-44)

As shared by T3, she prefers a traditional teaching approach with the use of direct instruction because in this method she can train the learners the way she wants to, and with this method she can also impose discipline effectively and focus on the content of the lesson. From her experience, she saw that the learners strive hard to meet the teacher's standard and get high scores.

The lines below are the insights gathered from T4's responses.

Ahh for me, my reasons for preferring the use of traditional approaches in teaching ahh materials are easy to prepare and ahh pupils are my students can easily get what I am teaching or what I am going to persuade about the lessons that I have because they can visualize easily what what are or what is the lesson all about. (T4, Lines 20-23)

T4 prefers traditional teaching approach as student can easily learn, persuade and visualize what the lesson is all about. The sole source of information is the instructor or professor, and under the direct instruction paradigm, teachers frequently follow scripted, methodical lesson plans. The particular phrases the teacher ought to use and the tasks the students should perform are included in direct instruction classes for each minute of the lessons.

Inculcates Discipline. The second core idea that emerges from the major theme Traditional Teaching Promotes Holistic Teaching and Learning Process is that it inculcates discipline. This core idea gathered typical responses. Students need discipline in school to succeed academically. Skinner et al. (2022) highlighted in their recent research that discipline is intimately related to the participation of learners and their behavior in the classroom. A disciplined classroom encourages active involvement, attention, and respect for others, all of which improve the learning process.

The lines below are T3's shared experience about how traditional teaching approach inculcates discipline.

Ahh in I think its ano (what) its traditional teaching because it's a one-way flow of information or direct instruction to the learners. In the traditional teaching approach, we can train the way we wanted to and, in that way, we can impose discipline effectively, we can focus on the content of the lesson and also, we can see the learners will strive hard to meet their standard and get high scores ahh and and please the teacher and also, they can pass the requirements. (T3, Lines 39-44)

According to T3, with traditional approaches to teaching, she can effectively impose discipline in her class. The fact that discipline in schools improves academic performance is one of the main justifications for placing a high focus on it. Discipline in the classroom helps keep students focused on their work while they are with the teacher, reducing interruptions and enhancing the flow of information. Based on the above-mentioned insight that I have drawn on how traditional approaches to teaching facilitate the teaching-learning process and inculcate discipline,

In Addition to that T4 also mentioned about imposing discipline to her student.

Yes, I am aware of the 21st century teaching and and learning but then, as I've said, again, I prefer traditional teaching because I feel comfortable of this. I can impose discipline to my pupils—to my pupils, and of course, I can—I can really bring out learnings for my pupils and of course, materials are easily to produce. The items that I have can be easily to produce. (T4, Lines 78-81)

From the statement of T4 above the insight that I have gathered from T4's response is inculcating discipline. According to T4 with the use of traditional teaching approach she is comfortable and can impose discipline to her pupils. She also added that she can really bring out learnings form her pupils with the use of this approach.

Discipline also has an impact on children's emotional well-being. Wilson et al. (2022), found that learners in a well-structured and disciplined setting have lower stress levels and increased willingness to learn. Discipline helps to shape the classroom culture. A disciplined classroom, according to Lewis and Novak (2019), develops a culture of respect, responsibility, and accountability among students, which improves the learning environment. Discipline affects not only students but also teacher satisfaction and well-being.

Enhances Learner Engagements. The third core idea from the major theme Traditional Teaching Promotes Holistic Teaching-Learning Process is Enhances Learner Engagements that gathered general responses from my participants.

Thus, in my research I found insight from T2 based on the lines below.

Yes, I do. I think its promo it promotes engagement in students because if you are going to form some groups were using ahmm traditional way like using papers, pens, ahh and doing their activities ahmm it I can see that they really enjoyed it, they cooperate with other other students ahmm considering also that if I'll use technology, only few students have their own gadget so we should we we opted to use ahmm the traditional ways ahmm chalk, and paper and ahh what they called it like bet "bitaymax" ahmm or using flashcards instead of using a power point in the lesson. Ahmm as as my observation, they they they learn they learned a lot with those methods. (T2, Lines 45-52)

For T2, traditional teaching still facilitates learning with engagements. T2 shared that traditional teaching still promote engagement through groupings and using papers, pens and doing their activities. She mentioned that from her experience she saw that the learners are enjoying and cooperating with the other learners. She also added that as her observation her students learned a lot with the traditional way of teaching.

T1 stated that traditional teaching promotes student engagement on her answer to the probing question does traditional teaching approach promotes engagement, the lines below are her statement.

Ahmm. Ahh yes. Somehow, I observed that my learners are silent, but they are listening. When I ask questions, they can give answer. (T1, Lines 30-31)

From the statement of T1 she mentioned that she observed that with the traditional approach to teaching her learners are somehow engage because the learners are silent but listening and when she asked questions the student can give answers. According to a research by Roberts et al. (2019), the traditional approach allows for more direct and immediate teacher-student engagement. Students' engagement with the topic can be increased through face-to-face talks, questions and answers, and personalized feedback.

T4 also shared her experience about the same question stating the lines below.

Like I have said a while ago that my pupils can easily get or can what you call what you can say that my student madali lang silang maka maka learn noh (the students learn fast) through visual or using traditional approaches because ahh ahh upon using powerpoint

or or computer, ah my pupils can ah what do you mean by that? Ah parang hindi enough ang time para sa kanila (the time is not enough for them) and besides, we don't have other materials to provide them para maka ah para maifit sila (for them to fit) for 21st century learning. (T4, Lines 27-33)

From T4's shared experience she stated that with the traditional teaching approach her pupils can easily learn. The traditional approach frequently places an emphasis on stated learning objectives and outcomes. In accordance with a study conducted by Lee et al. (2015), clearly defined goals can encourage students and provide a sense of purpose, improving their engagement with the subject matter.

T5 also shared his experience on, in what way does traditional teaching approach engage with the students.

Traditional teaching ah it engages student to explore more, mas nakaka explore yung mga studyante (the students can explore more) base from the activities given from the book, kasi nga yung mga (it's because) ah even though simplified na yung now a days na mga activities (the activities nowadays are already simplified), there are still ah there are still activities now a days lalo pa't (now that) we are in the 21st century, meron pa ring mga activities na hindi masyadong maintindihan nang mga bata. (There are still activities that the children cannot understand.) But, when it comes to other sources or other books traditional books ahmm K-12 books na (that) traditional yung pag yung techniques sa pagtuturo mas maiintindihan ng mga bata kasi (if the techniques in teaching is in traditional way, the children can understand it better) they can relate kasi nga now a days, yung mga libro (the books) is localize and ah naka tawag nito (what do we call this), naka localize (it's localize) and tawag nito kaniing (what do we call this it's), within the area nalang nang within the proximity nalang nang learning yung mga nadoon sa lesson (within the area only and witching the proximity only of the learning were there in the lesson.) Yun. (There) (T5, Lines 61-74)

According to T4, traditional teaching approaches engages students to explore more based from the activities given from the book. He also shared that even though we are in the 21st century there are still activities that the learners cannot understand. Because engagement is an essential condition for learning, student participation is seen as a crucial element of education.

Traditional Teaching is a Practical Way of Teaching

From the responses of my participants the second major theme that I have gathered is the Traditional Teaching is a Practical Way of Teaching. Conti (2017) defined the term teaching approach as the distinctive characteristics exhibited by a teacher that are consistent from situation to situation regardless of the content being taught. The teacher controls learning by offering the surroundings and technological tools that promote and enhance learners' capacity for critical thought and problem-solving. I considered techniques that encourage pupils to explain their understanding, logic, or problem-solving. From this major theme emerged the core ideas practical way of teaching, memorization and the use of bitay max.

Employs Realistic Way of Teaching. The first core idea that arise from the major theme is the Realistic Way of Teaching which gathers typical responses from the informants is the Practical Way of Teaching. In my study this simply refers to a method of applying someone's experience or a concept that is more concerned with or applicable to practice than theory.

As to my study, realistic way of teaching means using and utilizing any available and accessible instructional materials inside the classroom by the teacher to support the teaching and learning process. Instructional materials such as papers, pens, books and other materials that are traditionally used by teachers. When teachers teach practically, students find it easier to learn. If you want to be a good and influential teacher, you must use the appropriate teaching strategies and approaches. Teach practically is something that teachers are capable of.

The lines below are the statement of T1, when she answered the question, in what she can contribute to the 21st century learners with the use of traditional approaches to teaching.

What I can give is, I will passionately teach my learners according to my capability and I will utilize the available resources. If there are materials that could contributed to the 21st century teaching, I will use it and I would be thankful with that. (T1, Lines 75-78)

T1 shared that she would teach her learners passionately and according to her capability and she will utilize the available resources. Accordingly, if there are materials that could contribute to the 21st century teaching she will still use it and be thankful with it.

For T2, using the materials like paper and pens still makes her learners learn. The statement below are her lines.

Hmm for now, I would say ahmm both are the best but in my in my case, I would choose traditional traditional way of teaching because ahmm you have to consider your the finances, of course. Ahmm the materials that you have ahmm and and the level of students that we have ahmm because if you will going to use the other the modern type of the modern strategies you have to invest on on buying computers computer or loading your your wifi and they can learn if they have also their devices for for for learning. But in the traditional way, they can use paper and pen or manila paper and and pentel pens or paste or glue in doing their activities, its manipulative at the same time they were learning a lot. It's not it doesn't mean that traditional that it's the teacher who always does the job but ah using the traditional way of teaching by using ahmm paper and pens and other other things that are not related to technology, I think it also delivers learning to ah learners in a different way. (T2, Lines 61-71)

From the statement above, T2 mentioned that both teaching styles are best but she preferred traditional teaching approach because for

her the materials are easily provided.

Encourages Memorization. The second core idea that was brought out is Encourages Memorization which gathered variant responses from the participants. Memorization is often known as rote learning, is a learning method that involves repeatedly repeating facts and numbers. This knowledge is ingrained in the pupils' memory banks as a result of repetition.

Memorization also refers to an essential learning strategy that develops mental skills that last a lifetime.

For T2, memorization is really effective teaching technique because she learned the same way as mentioned in the lines below.

Well, it was brought up using traditional teaching and I learned a lot from those strategies that all my teacher when I was elementary and high school that are using ahmm I could say that I learned a lot from that I can even memorize or or or or recall the teach the lessons that I've learned from them. Ahmm so, I guest that is effective ahmm considering of of who ahh who I am right now. (T2, Lines 70-74)

From the statement of T2, she shared that through memorization she had learned a lot from her teachers during her student's life. She considered memorization is still effective because she learned that way.

Stimulates Resourcefulness of Teachers. The third core idea that arise from the major theme is the Stimulates Resourcefulness of Teachers which gathered typical response from the participants. Upon gathering information of the participants responded that in traditional approach to teaching they are being more creative and resourceful in providing their learners the learning materials for the lesson.

T5 stated his experience on the statements below.

So, kagaya nga nang sinabi ko kanina (just like I said a while ago), our educational system here in the Philippines is ahh naga evolve pa (still evolving) and its still improving, still learning in grasping 21st century teaching. So, we are not like other countries na(that) over advanced and all the resources are given. Now, here in the Philippines, we we tried our best na maging (to be) resourceful pa talaga kasi tayong mga teachers nga (because we teachers), we really find time to have this resources para mabigay sa mga studyante natin yung (to give our students the) quality ed quality education na kailangan nila (that they need). So, I still prefer traditional teaching ahh compared syem syempre (of course) traditional teaching with a touch of 21st century para hindi naman ma behind ang mga studyante natin (so that our students will not be left behind) when it comes 20 21st century learning. Yun. (There) (T5, Lines 112-121)

T5 claimed that teachers must be resourceful to give our learners the quality education that they need. The teaching methods, which are renowned for their traditional approach to education, as examined by Halupa and Caldwell (2015). He maintains that the regulated and predictable teaching strategies used in these schools encourage teachers to showcase their resourcefulness. Regardless of their background, teachers are expected to follow a set curriculum and are given access to materials and techniques that will guarantee that all learners obtain an excellent education.

T2 further shared:

Yes, I do. I think its promo it promotes engagement in students because if you are going to form some groups were using ahmm traditional way like using papers, pens, ahh and doing their activities ahmm it I can see that they really enjoyed it, they cooperate with other other students ahmm considering also that if I'll use technology, only few students have their own gadget so we should we we opted to use ahmm the traditional ways ahmm chalk, and paper and ahh what they called it like bet "bitaymax" ahmm or using flashcards instead of using a power point in the lesson. Ahmm as as my observation, they they they learn they learned a lot with those methods. (T2, Lines 45-52)

T2 mentioned that she uses "bitay max" instead of power point presentation ins her lessons. In addition, she has observed that the learners are learning a lot with this method. She showed that her being resourceful by using alternative learning materials such as "bitay max" to facilitate learning. The prospects and difficulties facing the educational system are examined by (Darling-Hammond, 2015). While she promotes more innovative and student-centered teaching strategies in her work, she also acknowledges that in order for teachers to serve their students effectively, they must be resourceful in dealing the challenges of the traditional approach.

In conclusion, the study highlights the reasons behind teachers' preference for traditional teaching approaches and the benefits they perceive in using such methods. The insights drawn from participants shed light on the practicality, cost-effectiveness, and effectiveness of traditional teaching in facilitating the teaching-learning process. Teachers' resourcefulness and adaptability in utilizing traditional materials demonstrate their commitment to providing quality education despite limitations in resources.

Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of traditional teaching methods in education, despite the rapid development of digital technology. At Lagao 2nd Bo. Elementary School, teachers preferred traditional methods due to their convenience, cost-effectiveness, and the old-school classroom atmosphere. Traditional methods were deemed easier to use, cost-effective, and more time-efficient, making them more effective in maintaining student engagement. The costs associated with traditional methods were lower than those of modern

methods, as they relied on easily accessible materials and face-to-face interaction, making them an affordable solution for institutions with limited resources. Traditional classroom formats offered opportunities for face-to-face interaction, structured timetables, and designated study hours. Despite potential isolation and concerns about academic integrity, teachers still viewed them as beneficial.

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